

Hydroxymethylfurfural: A key to increased reactivity and performance of fructose-based adhesives for particle boards

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ABSTRACT

There is a push towards the use of renewable adhesives in particle board manufacturing industry. A remaining barrier for the successful implementation of carbohydrate-based adhesives is the necessity of a rapid cure behavior at lower temperatures (105–120 °C). The aim of this work was to study the effect of highly reactive, bio-based 5-Hydroxymethylfurfural (HMF) on the cure speed in fructose-bis(hexamethylenetriamine) (BHMT) adhesive. The technological suitability of these adhesives for the intended application in particle boards was done by combining adhesive characterization with thermal analysis and tensile shear strength development. Overall, HMF had a strong, positive effect on the reactivity and performance of these fructose-based adhesives, especially at lower hot-press temperatures. The tensile shear strength development of fructose/HMF/BHMT adhesives was comparable to commercial, fossil-based urea-formaldehyde resin at 120 °C. A sufficient tensile shear strength of 5.0 ± 0.3 N/mm² was reached after press times as low as 30 s and 6.2 ± 0.1 N/mm² after pressing for 150 s at 105 °C. This suggests fructose-HMF-BHMT adhesives have sufficient reactivity and performance and as such are a promising adhesive for a cleaner production of particle boards. Their rapid cure behavior is among the best of previously reported HMF-based adhesives.

1. Introduction

Adhesive-bonded structures are widely used in various industries, such as the civil engineering (Mays, 1985), automotive (Cavezza et al., 2020) or aircraft branches, as well as the wood product manufacturing sector (Stoeckel et al., 2013). Wood adhesives make up more than 65% of all adhesives used in the world, making wood product manufacturing the largest adhesive user by volume (Pizzi, 2016). In 2018, particle boards had a percentage share of 50% of the European production of wood-based panels (Fig. 1), with the majority of them (63%) being used for furniture.

Today mainly formaldehyde-based adhesives, such as urea-formaldehyde (UF) are used in particle board production (Clad, 1983).

The dominant position of these petrochemical adhesives is based on their excellent bonding performance as well as the quality and strength of the thereof produced wood panel boards. Over the years, the emission of formaldehyde has become a subject of concern. Recently formaldehyde was reclassified as cancerogenic by the International Agency for Research and Cancer (IARC) and the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA) (Commission; and E, 2014; Popović et al., 2020). These increasing regulations about volatile organic compound emissions and public concern about fossil resources has led to increased research on alternative, formaldehyde-emission free adhesives for the cleaner production of particle boards (Arias et al., 2021; Jiang et al., 2017).

The reactivity of the curing adhesive, more precisely its cure speed, is an essential criterion. It defines the technical suitability and economic

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feasibility for the application in particle boards. Solt et al. (2019) evaluated the technical performance of alternative carbohydrate-based adhesives reported in literature and found that the majority is significantly less reactive than the adhesives found in today's industry. The adhesive development is made even more complicated by the fact that during particle board production the temperature in the core layer is limited to below 120 °C due to the presence of water vapor and the resulting gas pressure within the panel (see Fig. 2) (Solt et al., 2019). Thus, the reactivity of a wood adhesive cannot be further increased by simply using the temperature dependency of the reaction rate.

A very interesting approach for increasing the reactivity of carbohydrate-based adhesives is the (partial) conversion of these carbohydrates into more reactive compounds. 5-hydroxymethylfurfural (HMF) is a very suitable candidate in that regard with a high but as yet almost untapped potential as key reactant in wood adhesives (Kong et al., 2020; Rosenfeld et al., 2020). In general, HMF can be produced via acidic dehydration reaction from surplus carbohydrate feedstocks, for example fructose. The principle idea that HMF could contribute to the crosslinking of carbohydrate-based resins was already postulated in 1926 (Meigs, 1926), but research on HMF-containing adhesives is still in its infancy (Rosenfeld et al., 2020).

In a previous rheokinetic study, we found that 5 mol.-% HMF increases the reactivity of fructose- bishexamethylenetriamine (BHMT) adhesives by lowering the activation energy of the curing reaction (Thoma et al., 2021). Although these findings underline its high potential, a throughout evaluation of its effect on cure speed and strength development is needed to determine the technological suitability of this adhesive in particle boards.

In this work, we want to investigate the tensile shear strength development especially in the low temperature curing range (105–120 °C) which is essential for the particle board core layer. We hypothesize that the reduced activation energy of fructose-HMF-BHMT adhesives also reflects on the material performance and improves the cure speed of those adhesives. Therefore, fructose-BHMT without HMF was tested as reference adhesive. Potential composition-property relations were analyzed by testing the tensile shear strength for different adhesive compositions varying in molar ratio and molecular weight. The overall aim of this work is to evaluate the adhesives curing efficiency by further studying the temperature-dependent material behavior and to see if the results from adhesive testing can be transported to prototype particle boards.

2. Experimental section

2.1. Materials

An industrial Core Layer E1 UF resin, supplied by Fritz Egger GmbH & CO. OG (Unterradlberg, Austria), was used as the reference adhesive

for the mechanical testing. Fructose solution FF95 (70.5% dry solids, 95% purity) and crystalline fructose FF100 (purity 99.5%) was supplied by Cargill Deutschland GmbH (Krefeld, Germany). An aqueous HMF solution (comprising 60 g/L HMF, 214 g/L fructose) was produced in a mesoreactor and used without purification. The HMF production procedure was described previously (Sailer-Kronlachner et al., 2021). The HMF solution was stored at 7 °C. Bishexamethylenetriamine (BHMT) (crystalline, high purity) and ammonium nitrate were purchased from Sigma Aldrich (St. Luis, MO, U.S.A.). Crystalline HMF, supplied by Sigma Aldrich (St. Luis, MO, U.S.A.) was used for comparative FTIR analysis. Seven, analytical grade, dextran standards varying in molecular weight (M_w : 5000, 25,000, 50,000, 150,000, 270,000, 410,000, 670,000) were purchased from Sigma Aldrich (St. Luis, MO, U.S.A.) for the GPC analysis.

2.2. HMF production in a mesoreactor

In a previous work our group developed an in-situ process, which contained HMF synthesis and adhesive production (Sailer-Kronlachner et al., 2021). This approach paves the way for the utilization of HMF as a reactive compound in carbohydrate-based adhesives, as it reduces the dependency on expensive pure HMF. An aqueous fructose solution (10% fructose) was heated to 162 °C for 0.92 min with 1% sulfuric acid as catalyst in a continuous flow mesoreactor setup. The resulting aqueous precursor solution comprised of 24 g/L HMF, which was concentrated to 60 g/L HMF. This HMF-rich solution (60 g/L HMF, 214 g/L residual sugars) was not purified but was directly used in the sub-sequent adhesive production, which is described in more detail in 2.3.2.

2.3. Resin synthesis

2.3.1. Fructose/BHMT

Fructose FF95 was neutralized with 1 M sodium hydroxide, added to a three-necked flask, equipped with a thermo-element and a reflux condenser, and heated to 60 °C under magnetic stirring on a hot plate equipped with a PTFE coated heating attachment. The following molar fructose/BHMT ratios were studied: 5.2/1, 3.9/1 and 2.6/1. The BHMT equivalent was separated in two equal portions, of which the first half was added to the carbohydrate solution during the heating process, when 40 °C were reached, and the second portion directly before the analysis. The reaction time was varied and reactions were stopped by letting it cooling to room temperature after 15 min, 20 min, 30 min, 45 min, 60 min, 75 min and 90 min. The target solid content after the second addition of amine was 60 wt.-%.

2.3.2. Fructose/HMF/BHMT

5 wt.-% of the fructose used in the above fructose/BHMT resin procedure was substituted with HMF. This resulted in fructose/HMF/BHMT

Fig. 1. Left: European production of wood-based panels in 2018 (adapted from ("Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations Forest Products Annual Market Review 2018–2019," 2019 (Food and Agriculture, 2019))), Right: European uses for particle boards during 2019 (adapted from (Federation, 2018)).

Fig. 2. Temperature development in center and surface layer of a single-layer particle board made out of compressed core layer wood particles in a 50 × 50 cm laboratory hot press at 220 °C press temperature, adapted from (Solt et al., 2019).–.

molar ratios of 4.9/0.3/1, 3.7/0.2/1, and 2.5/0.1/1. The procedure of the resin synthesis was the same as above for the fructose/BHMT adhesives, except that water-based HMF solution was added together with the fructose at the beginning of the synthesis. In order to avoid unintended curing during storage, the second BHMT portion was added short before the material testing.

2.4. Solid content

The conventional solid content of the resins was measured according to EN 827:2005 (DIN, 2005). A clean aluminum container (60 mm inner diameter) was prepared according to the standard procedure, and then 2.0 ± 0.2 g of the produced resin was heated at 120 ± 1 °C for 120 ± 1 min in an oven.

2.5. Automated bonding evaluation system (ABES)

The reactivity of the developed adhesive systems was measured with an automated bonding evaluation system (ABES) (Humphrey, 1993). The tests were performed according to ASTM-D7998–15 (ASTM International:West Conshohocken PA, 2015). Uniform, planar and defect-free European beech veneers ($120 \times 20 \times 0.6$ mm) were used for the tests. Prior to the test, the veneers were stored at standardized climate of 20 °C with 65% relative humidity. 125 g/m^2 resin (dry weight) were applied to the overlapping area of the joint (20 mm x 5 mm). The samples were hot pressed at either 120 °C, 110 °C or 105 °C using the ABES testing device. The press time was varied between 15 s and 600 s. After the pressing, tensile force was applied and the tensile shear strength of the joint was calculated. Since the produced resins showed thermoplastic material behavior, a cooling phase was applied right after hot pressing in all measurements, done by blowing air (room temperature) onto the adhesive joint for 30 s or 60 s. In preliminary experiments, a thermoelement was used to measure the temperature profile in the bondline during hot-pressing and subsequent cooling. Cooling the bondline from 120 °C or 105 °C for 60 s reduced its temperature to $35 \text{ °C} \pm 3 \text{ °C}$. Aqueous ammonium nitrate solution (15% w/w) was used as hardener and mixed with the UF resin in a (liquid on liquid) weight ratio of 1:10 in the measurements of the reference adhesive system.

2.6. Infrared spectroscopy (FTIR)

The educts (crystalline fructose, HMF, BHMT) and the produced adhesives were analyzed on a FTIR spectrometer (Vertex 70, Bruker, Billerica, USA) equipped with a PIKE MIRacle™ ATR sampling accessory (PIKE Technologies, Madison, USA) and a pyroelectric detector RT-DLaTGS (deuterated L-alanine doped triglycine sulphate). An air spectrum was recorded as background before each measurement and subtracted. Each sample was added directly to the ATR unit and measured with a pressure stamp. The samples were analyzed in the range from

4000 cm^{-1} to 600 cm^{-1} with 4 cm^{-1} for one data point, measuring 32 scans in total. The samples were freeze dried for 48 h prior to analysis.

2.7. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) was used as thermoanalytical method to characterize the thermal behavior of the adhesives (Polyma 214, Netzsch-Gerätebau GmbH, Germany). 5 mg of uncured adhesive sample were measured in a closed, high-pressure steel crucible. Non-isothermal measurements were performed from 50 °C to 250 °C at a heating rate of 5 °C/min. An empty, identical crucible was used as reference. Data analysis was performed with the Netzsch Proteus® software (Netzsch-Gerätebau GmbH, Selb, Germany).

2.8. Gel permeation chromatography (GPC)

Uncured adhesive samples were dissolved in DMSO at a concentration of 2 mg/mL and filtered through 0.45 µm syringe filters. Gel permeation chromatography was carried out at 30 °C on an Agilent Technologies HPLC System (Agilent Technologies 1260 Infinity, Santa Clara, CA, USA) with a 50×80 mm MZ-Gel SDplus LS 10E5Å 10 µm guard column and a 300×8.0 mm MZ-Gel SDplus LS linear 10 µm liquid chromatography column (MZ Analysetechnik, Mainz, Germany) with DMSO as mobile phase at a flow rate of 1 mL/min. An Agilent Technologies G1362A refractive index detector was used. The molecular weights of the uncured adhesives were calculated based on dextran standards (M_w of 5000, 25,000, 50,000, 150,000, 270,000, 410,000, 670,000). Injection volume was 20 µL. Samples were taken at different stages of the adhesive synthesis to follow the polymerization process (see Supporting Information, Tables 1 and 2).

2.9. Particle board preparation and testing

Industrial-grade core layer wood particles (moisture content 7.6 wt.-%) and 10% adhesive (based on the dry weight of the particles) were used in the preparation of one-layered laboratory particle boards. The fructose/HMF/BHMT adhesive was used directly without additional hardeners. The second portion of BHMT (see the above preparation protocol) was added before applying the adhesive to the wood particles. The adhesive was poured onto the wood particles and homogenized for 15 min in a ploughshare mixer (FM50E/1MZ 1976, Gebrüder Lödige Maschinenbau GmbH, Germany). The particle boards (40 cm x 40 cm) were pressed in a hydraulic hot press (LZT-OK 175 L, Langzauner GmbH, Lambrecht, Austria) at a press temperature of 220 °C. Metal spacing strips with a thickness of 15 mm were used. The target density of the boards was 650 g/cm^3 . The produced boards were stored for 14 days at standard climate, more specifically at an average moisture content of 65% and an average temperature of 20 °C, to fulfill the requirements of the standardized testing procedure given in the European standard

Table 1

Number-average molecular weight (M_n), weight-average molecular weight (M_w), dispersity (D_M), pH and solid content for adhesive with different fructose/HMF/BHMT molar ratios.

Molar ratio Fructose/(HMF)/BHMT	Synthesis time [min]	M_n [kDa]	M_w [kDa]	D_M	pH	Solid content [%]
3.7/0.2/1	15	24.45	28.94	1.18	11.1	58.3
	30	26.19	30.86	1.18	10.7	58.4
	45	29.87	48.77	1.63	10.6	61.1
	60	34.57	72.97	2.11	10.2	59.3
3.9/-/1	15	24.31	37.39	1.54	11.3	53.5
	60	23.74	37.53	1.58	11.2	55.1
2.5/0.1/1	15	28.86	41.23	1.43	10.8	63.6
	30	30.15	33.14	1.10	10.8	64.2
2.6/-/1	15	28.71	38.29	1.33	10.8	55.0
	60	34.57	41.06	1.19	10.4	55.3
4.9/0.3/1	15	19.04	33.51	1.76	10.5	57.4
	60	26.88	32.94	1.22	10.1	58.1
5.2/-/1	15	20.93	26.76	1.28	10.9	53.0
	60	26.38	48.97	1.85	10.3	53.4
UF Reference	-	-	-	-	9.0	66.0

EN319 (Standarization, 1993). The determination of the internal bond strength perpendicular to the plane of the board (IB) was carried out in accordance with the European standard EN319 (Standarization, 1993) on a universal testing machine Z020 (Zwick GmbH&CO.KG, Ulm, Germany). The modulus of rupture (MOR) and modulus of elasticity (MOE) were calculated from bending tests according to the European standard EN310 (Standard, 2005a). MOR and MOE provide information on the quality of the face layer of a particle board. The swelling in thickness after immersion in water for 24 h was tested according to the European standard EN317 (Standard, 2005b). Test pieces (50 × 50 mm) were cut from the particle boards. Thickness and weight of each test piece were measured at the intersection of the diagonals before and after immersion.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Sustainability considerations

Up to now, no large-scale, industrial HMF plant is operating. This also reflects on the high price of HMF (Sigma Aldrich 3980 €/kg, 03.08.2021) and low quantities of HMF available on the market. The material cost of fructose/HMF/BHMT adhesives can be significantly reduced when an in-situ approach is used. In a previously reported work from our group, an in-situ production was realized which couples the HMF synthesis and subsequent adhesive production (Sailer-Kronlachner et al., 2021). In-situ approaches increase the efficiency and sustainability of the adhesive production, as it eliminates expensive, time and resource-consuming separation and purification steps of HMF. Unfortunately, most of the reported HMF production methods in literature are incompatible with subsequent adhesive production. Ideally, water is

Table 2

Characteristic temperatures of the deconvoluted DSC peaks for the curing of fructose/HMF/BHMT adhesives with and without second addition of amine.

Fructose/HMF/BHMT w/o 2 nd amine	Onset temperature [°C]	Peak temperature [°C]	End temperature [°C]	Area [J/g]	Percentage share [%]
Peak 1	80.5	111.5	143.9	137.2	23.6
Peak 2	129.5	141.8	154.2	2.9	0.5
Peak 3	130.4	174.3	208.8	335.2	71.4
Peak 4	197.4	207.9	224.6	6.2	1.1
Peak 5	197.1	219.4	239.5	18.9	3.4
Fructose/HMF/BHMT with 2nd amine					
Peak 1	65.3	78.9	92.7	8.5	1.3
Peak 2	79.3	112.4	167.5	409.4	76.8
Peak 3	138.7	146.2	155.5	2.7	0.4
Peak 4	141.1	165.7	205	113.5	19.5
Peak 5	180.4	208.9	233.1	12.3	1.9

used as a green solvent and mineral acids as catalyst, e.g. sulfuric acid, because they can remain in the produced adhesive. Sailer-Kronlachner et al. (Sailer-Kronlachner et al., 2021) reported the sulfuric acid-catalyzed dehydration of fructose to HMF in different reaction systems, which is compatible with a subsequent production of fructose/HMF/BHMT resins. The production of HMF itself is environmentally friendly, and water that can also be used as solvent in the subsequent resin production, is considered the “greenest” available solvent. The low HMF yields of 38–49% in aqueous solutions (Sailer-Kronlachner et al., 2021) are an issue needing attention when coupling HMF and adhesive production. As such, the maximum amount of HMF in the adhesives is limited by the obtained HMF concentration in the production process. Only small amounts of HMF (5% based on fructose content) are used in the fructose-HMF-BHMT adhesives that we communicate in this study. Previous publications indicated that already the addition of 5% HMF was sufficient for enhanced adhesive performance (Sailer-Kronlachner et al., 2021).

3.2. Adhesive characterization

3.2.1. Possible structural elements of the adhesive system

Several possible reactions can lead to the complex polymeric structures formed in fructose-HMF-BHMT adhesives. Examples are the self-condensation of HMF to humin-like structures, reaction of HMF and BHMT and formation of fructosylamines and further Maillard products (see Fig. 3).

In another publication, we propose that HMF reacts with itself in condensation reactions, aldol-like reactions and by attack on the furan ring system (Sailer-Kronlachner et al., 2022). These reactions lead to the formation of dimers and oligomers, which can further react to form humins. These humins are often an unwanted side-product in HMF production and were analyzed in more detail in Sailer-Kronlachner et al. (Sailer-Kronlachner et al., 2022) via chemical analysis via FTIR, ¹³C NMR and solid state NMR.

Based on the conducted FTIR analysis (see 3.2.2), we propose that the base structure of BHMT is contained in the resin and crosslinking occurs via the free amine moieties. The amine groups in BHMT can furthermore react with HMFs aldehyde and hydroxyl moieties, leading to further crosslinking.

The complex network of reactions between reducing sugars and compounds containing free amino groups is known as the Maillard reaction (Barclay et al., 2012). In the initial stage, the keto carbonyl group of fructose and the amine condense to a Schiff-base, which is then isomerized to fructosylamine. Then new carbonyl products, formed by a Heyns rearrangement, can further react to various intermediates leading to high molecular weight melanoidins. There is a wide choice of literature reviews looking at the Maillard reaction from different perspectives (chemistry, food technology, medicine) (Bastos and Gugliucci, 2015; Somoza, 2005; Zhang et al., 2009), but the complex mechanism of the Maillard reaction is still a controversial issue (Martins et al., 2000).

The aim of the adhesive characterization conducted in this work was

Fig. 3. Possible reactions leading to complex polymeric structures in Fructose-HMF-BHMT adhesives (proposed humin structural element from Sailer-Kronlachner et al.).

to find further evidence that HMF reacts in the adhesive synthesis, for example by indicative FTIR analysis. Potential structural elements of the adhesive are not discussed in more detail as they would be highly speculative given the number and complexity of the reaction system and their potential dependency on synthesis parameters (e.g. temperature, pH). A statement on the reaction mechanism and the structural incorporation of HMF in the adhesive can only be made after a more rigorous chemical analysis, for example using ^{13}C - or ^{15}N -selective labeling.

3.2.2. FTIR analysis

Fig. 4 shows the spectra of fructose, BHMT, 5-HMF, a fructose/BHMT resin and a fructose/HMF/BHMT resin.

The fructose/HMF/BHMT adhesives contained only 5% HMF relative to fructose. Because of this, bands from HMF were rather weak and could not afford much information about the incorporation of HMF into the final resin and its chemical fate. However, it was evident that the prominent $\text{C}=\text{O}$ peak of HMF at 1660 cm^{-1} completely disappeared in the resin, implying that the HMF aldehyde moiety has been consumed and is incorporated into the complex resin structure. The peak at 1560 cm^{-1} can either be a result of an aromatic ring vibration ($\text{C}=\text{C}$, either from a furan ring or newly formed aromatic compounds) or a bending vibration of a N-H bond, which would indicate that non reacted $-\text{NH}_2$ or $-\text{NH}$ groups were still present in the resin. Signals at $1410\text{--}1250\text{ cm}^{-1}$ can be attributed to different $-\text{OH}$ and CO vibrations. The comparison of the spectra of the fructose/BHMT (3.9:1) and the fructose/HMF/BHMT (3.7:0.2:1) resins showed slight differences in peak intensity but no clear signals that could be attributed to the additional presence of 5-HMF. The broad and intense peak between 950 and 1150 cm^{-1} can be attributed to ether bonds newly formed through condensation reactions and the $\text{C}-\text{O}-\text{C}$ bond of the furan ring system of

Fig. 4. Infrared spectra of fructose/BHMT and fructose/HMF/BHMT adhesives in comparison to the educts fructose FF100 (crystalline), BHMT and HMF (crystalline).

HMF (1020 cm^{-1}) (Al Ghatta et al., 2021). The C-C double bond vibrations of the furan ring at 1520 cm^{-1} were not found in the resin spectra, which indicates a reaction of the ring system upon polymerization. C-H vibrations at 780 cm^{-1} cannot be clearly attributed to HMF - they more likely result from fructose due to the higher fructose concentration in the resin or aromatic structures possibly formed. The region above 2500 cm^{-1} is less conclusive and dominated by a huge, ill-resolved OH/NH/CH region. The methylene signals of the BHMT carbon chain remain clearly visible in the product resin, indicating that this carbon chain remains intact during the reaction. BHMT displays a slightly different pattern in this region, indicating that the amino groups of BHMT reacted during polymerization.

The FTIR analysis provided some first insights and indicated that HMF is incorporated into the complex resin structure. This underlines findings from a previous rheokinetic study, which found that fructose-HMF-BHMT has a significantly lower activation energy for the curing reaction than fructose-BHMT. It must be pointed out that an in-depth chemical characterization is a challenging task given the complexity of the polymeric structure of fructose-BHMT adhesives and the low amounts of HMF used in the resin. Further characterization of the resin structure, including NMR spectroscopy are part of a follow-up publication.

3.2.3. Molar mass

The molecular weight was analyzed at different stages of the adhesive synthesis to monitor the polymerization progress. The number-averaged molecular weight M_n , weight-averaged molecular weight M_w and the dispersity (D_M) of the uncured adhesives are given in Table 1. The GPC analysis indicated that the uncured adhesives consist of two fractions with different molecular weight. Additional adhesive characteristics, such as solid content and pH, are included as well. In general, all adhesives had a similar pH and solid content. The pH decreases

slightly during synthesis which can be explained by the consumption of amine. As expected, the molecular weight of the adhesive increased with longer synthesis times and higher BHMT contents. A very important finding is that HMF speeded up the polymerization process leading to a higher molecular weight (M_n and M_w) at shorter synthesis times. This effect can be seen especially well for the fructose/HMF/BHMT molar ratio of 3.7/0.2/1 compared to fructose/BHMT (without HMF) of 3.9/1 (see Table 1).

3.3. Thermal properties

DSC was used to analyze the thermal effects occurring upon curing of fructose-amine and fructose-HMF-amine adhesives. The range studied was $50\text{--}250\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. As seen in Fig. 5, there are two broad DSC peaks for which the peak fitting function of the analysis software suggests up to five underlying processes (Table 2). Peak 1 and 2 mainly contribute to the low-temperature curing of the adhesives, whereas the peaks at higher temperatures are most likely attributed to energetically less favored degradation or condensation processes. In the HMF-containing adhesives these processes possibly also involve humins, which are present in the HMF precursor solution (see Supporting Information, Fig. 1).

With regard to the intended application in particle boards, only peak 1 contributes to the curing of the adhesive in the core layer of the board. The underlying reactions are significantly influenced by the amount of BHMT that is added after the synthesis. The second portion of BHMT, added directly before material analysis and testing, enhances the low temperature curing reaction ($T_{\text{Peak2}} = 112.4\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$).

The detected Peak 5 ($T_{\text{Peak5}} = 219.4\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) of the fructose/HMF/BHMT adhesive without 2nd amine addition is caused by the degradation of the fructose FF95 (see Supporting Information, Fig. 1). This peak is not observed when a second portion of amine is added before the analysis (Table 2). This indicates that the added second addition of BHMT fully

Fig. 5. Thermal analysis (DSC) of a fructose/HMF/BHMT adhesive (3.7/0.2/1, 60 min) without addition of a second aliquot of BHMT before analysis (upper plot) and with addition of a second aliquot (middle plot) in comparison to fructose/BHMT (2.6/1, 15 min) (lower plot).

consumed residual fructose upon curing. The characteristic temperatures of the detected peaks are given in Table 2.

The high complexity of the curing reaction makes it complicated to determine the conversion endpoint. It is thus not possible to use the non-isothermal DSC data in an isoconversional analysis due to the overlapping of the peaks. A kinetic analysis of fructose/HMF/amine adhesives based on rheological measurements was done in a previous study (Thoma et al., 2021), proving that the addition of HMF had a positive effect on the curing of fructose-amine adhesives. In addition, isoconversional methods based on rheological data indicated a multi-step curing reaction.

3.4. Strength development of adhesive bonds

A standardized test method, the automated bonding evaluation system (ABES test), was used in investigating the effect of temperature on the cohesive strength development as function of pressing time using lab shear bonds under tensile loading (ASTM International:West Conshohocken PA, 2015). As shear stress is a common interfacial stress under service condition, ABES is often taken as a tool to tailor adhesive cure characteristics. The maximum tensile shear strength value in the performed tests was 6–7 N/mm² and it is attributed to the limited strength of beech veneers, which are typically used hardwood adherends (Gaff et al., 2016). The wood failure reached almost 100% at this strength.

3.5. Thermoplastic material behavior

A previously conducted analysis of the rheological properties of fructose/HMF/amine adhesives indicated a thermoplastic materials response (Thoma et al., 2021). In our study, a cooling interval was included to adjust the test temperature as suggested in ASTM-D7998–15 (ASTM International:West Conshohocken PA, 2015), using a 60 s cooling step to consistently reach a bondline temperature of 35–38 °C even after longer hot-pressing times (see Fig. 5, right plot).

The fructose/HMF/BHMT (3.7/0.2/1, synthesis time: 15 min) mixture showed a rapid strength development already at short press times below 150 s when a 60 s cooling step was applied (see Fig. 6, left plot). This underlines the thermoplastic material behavior of these fructose-based adhesives.

A conventional, core-layer E1 UF resin was used as the benchmark for a rapid cure behavior. Fructose/HMF/BHMT resins with a ratio of 3.7/0.2/1, ($T_{\text{press}}=120\text{ °C}$, 60 s cooling) had a tensile shear strength of $5.13 \pm 0.84\text{ N/mm}^2$ after hot-pressing for 90 s. The cure speed of fructose/HMF/BHMT is only 60 s slower than that of a conventional UF resin. The UF resin was cured with ammonium nitrate as hardener and

had a tensile shear strength of 6 N/mm² already after 30 s

The thermoplastic behavior of the studied fructose-based adhesives must be taken into consideration when testing the bond strength by adapting a cooling step before testing. In general, a 60 s cooling phase was used to adjust the testing temperature to about $35\text{ °C} \pm 3\text{ °C}$. Even though formaldehyde-based adhesives, such as UF, have a thermosetting material response, many other alternative adhesives, such as lignin-phenol-formaldehyde resins, are also known to exhibit a distinctive thermoplastic material behavior (Solt et al., 2019).

3.6. Influence of molar ratio fructose/HMF/BHMT on tensile shear strength

In general, the mechanical strength of a polymer increases with rising molecular weight and reaches a plateau at some point. As seen in Table 1, the molecular weight of the adhesives increased with rising synthesis time and presumably also further during curing in the consecutive hot-pressing time. In order to investigate the influence of different molar ratios, the tensile shear strength was measured as function of synthesis time (Fig. 7, A-B). Considering the temperature gradient from the core of the particle board to the outer layers during hot pressing (see Fig. 2), a rapid cure is necessary throughout a wide range of temperatures (105–200 °C). A press temperature of 105 °C and a press time of 150 s was chosen for the measurements, while tensile shear strength testing was done after 60 s cooling.

For the fructose/BHMT adhesives the plateau of the tensile shear strength was already reached at short synthesis times (see Fig. 7, A), with an increase in molecular weight (Table 1), which did not further improve the mechanical performance. In general, the adhesive bond performance between wood adherends is influenced by the degree of penetration of the adhesive into the porous network of the adherent according to the European standard EN923. This is controlled not only by substrate (i.e. wood species, moisture content) and processing variables (i.e. temperature, press time), but also by the molecular weight of the adhesive and its distribution (Gardner et al., 2015). The high molecular weight impedes the penetration so that no further improvement in mechanical performance is observed. Besides this, it must also be considered that the molecular weight of the adhesives further increases during curing (hot pressing). The fructose/BHMT adhesives showed an increase in tensile shear strength with increasing amine content (Fig. 7, C).

This correlation was not found for HMF-containing adhesives (Fig. 7, D). Rather, there seemed to be an optimum ratio around 3.7/0.2/1 (corresponding to 24 mol% BHMT, Fig. 6 D). The analysis of molecular weight showed that at higher amine contents (32 mol%), the influence of HMF in the precursor synthesis was negligible (Table 1). It can be

Fig. 6. Left: Influence of a cooling step on the tensile properties for fructose/HMF/BHMT (3.7/0.2/1, synthesis time: 15 min) adhesives pressed at 120 °C and tested at different temperatures. The UF reference was mixed 10:1 (liquid/ liquid) with (NH₄)NO₃ as the hardener. Right: temperature profile in the bondline after cooling from 120 °C (right).

Fig. 7. Tensile shear strength (pressed at 105 °C for 150 s, 60 s cooling) as function of synthesis time for fructose/BHMT (A) and fructose/HMF/BHMT adhesives (B). Tensile shear strength (pressed at 105 °C for 150 s, 60 s cooling) as function of BHMT amount in fructose/BHMT (C) and fructose-HMF/BHMT adhesives (D).

noted that also the tensile shear strength of these adhesive compositions, 2.6/1 and 2.5/0.1/1, was rather similar. The tensile shear strength in the lower graphs of (Fig. 7) is the averaged tensile shear strength of the plateau in the higher graphs.

A significant increase in tensile shear strength was observed up to synthesis times of 45 min for the fructose/HMF/BHMT adhesives (see Fig. 7, B). This was especially pronounced for the HMF-containing adhesives with lower BHMT contents. These findings suggest that an additional reaction involving HMF was taking place at longer synthesis time for the fructose/HMF/BHMT (3.7/0.2/1) adhesive. Based on the results, the most promising adhesives in terms of mechanical performance were fructose/BHMT (2.6/1, 20 min) and fructose/HMF/BHMT (3.7/0.2/1, 60 min).

3.7. Influence of press temperature on tensile shear strength

It is well known that in general the rate of a chemical reaction increases with increasing temperature. This can also be seen in the bond strength development of fructose/HMF/BHMT (Fig. 7, A-C) and fructose/BHMT (Fig. 7, D-F) measured at different press temperatures of 105 °C, 110 °C and 120 °C (60 s cooling). An important finding is that none of the tested adhesives reached a plateau value of tensile shear strength before dominating adherend failure. Above 6 N/mm² the failure mode was dominated by adherend failure, above this value there is only limited information value from the strength development of the adhesives.

When pressed at 105 °C there was no significant difference in the strength development of fructose/HMF/BHMT 4.9/0.3/1 (45 min) and 3.7/0.2/1 (60 min). In the fructose/HMF/BHMT 4.9/0.3/1 has a lower

amine content than 3.7/0.2/1, but the tensile shear strength is not reduced as is the case for the corresponding fructose/BHMT adhesives. This suggests that HMF plays a critical role in the strength development at low temperatures (105 °C) and compensates the lack of amine crosslinker to some degree. This effect is not observed in adhesives with a higher amine content (fructose/HMF/BHMT: 2.5/0.1/1), indicating a competitive reaction of HMF with the amine. At higher press temperatures (120 °C), fructose/HMF/BHMT with a molar ratio of 3.7/0.2/1 (60 min synthesis time) showed a faster strength development and reached overall higher tensile shear strength values than the other HMF-based adhesive compositions (Fig. 7, plot C).

It has to be highlighted that fructose/HMF/BHMT (3.7/0.2/1, 60 min) had the fastest strength development of all tested adhesives at the studied press temperatures (Fig. 7, D-F). At prolonged synthesis time of 60 min, fructose/HMF/BHMT (3.7/0.2/1, 60 min) showed a rapid strength development comparable to the UF reference even at temperatures as low as 105 °C. With a tensile shear strength of 6.2 ± 0.1 N/mm² after 150 s at 105 °C, fructose/HMF/BHMT (3.7/0.2/1, 60 min) had also the best performance. The results clearly demonstrated that the addition of HMF as additional reactive compound in the adhesive synthesis improved the strength development and enhanced the cure speed.

Previous findings (Fig. 6, A) showed that the cure speed of fructose/BHMT adhesives were enhanced by increasing the amount of BHMT to 2.6/1. As BHMT is the only compound that is fossil-based in the adhesive, increasing its amount in the resin recipe comes at the expense of “sustainability” of the system. Fig. 7 (E-F) shows that the tensile shear strength of the fructose/BHMT mixture with a molar ratio of 3.9/1 did not increase for temperatures above 110 °C. The previous rheokinetic analysis of fructose/BHMT adhesives (Thoma et al., 2021) found

evidence of the curing reaction being kinetically hindered at some point, which verifies the results from the tensile shear strength evaluation.

3.8. Particle board testing

Prototype particle boards were produced with the fructose/HMF/BHMT (3.7/0.2/1, 60 min) to see whether the results from ABES testing can be transferred to the intended application. The herein-studied adhesives are developed for the application in particle boards for interior furniture production. The corresponding classification according to European standard EN312 is P2 (Standarization, 1993), which refers to particle boards for interior fitments (including furniture) for the use in dry conditions. The internal bond strength (IB), defined as the tensile strength perpendicular to the plane of the particle board, is an important quality parameter for the adhesion of the core layer. Another important process-related parameter is the press factor. It is defined as the time needed to cure 1 mm of the panel cross-section.

The rate at which the bonding strength develops during hot-pressing critically affects the IB and press factor. The produced particle boards made with fructose/HMF/BHMT adhesive are compared to UF-boards. The minimum requirements for P2 (EN312) (Standarization, 1993) are

added as dashed lines in the plots (Fig. 8, A, C, D). In the previous ABES testing, the development of tensile shear strength was quite comparable for UF and fructose/HMF/BHMT (3.7/0.2/1, 60 min). (plot A) shows that significantly longer press times (>14 s/mm) are needed to reach minimum requirements of P2 for fructose/HMF/BHMT boards than for the reference UF. Fig. 9.

The IB strength of the tested fructose/HMF/BHMT particle boards are $0.29 \pm 0.09 \text{ N/mm}^2$ at a press factor of 14 s/mm and $0.39 \pm 0.10 \text{ N/mm}^2$ at 20 s/mm. This meets the target value of industrial three-layered P2 particle boards being $\geq 0.35 \text{ N/mm}^2$ (EN319) (Standarization, 1993), but overall the IB development of fructose/HMF/BHMT is slower than in UF-particle boards. This can also be seen by visual inspection of the core layer bondline of FHB bonded particle boards as shown in Fig. 10. At 10 s/mm the core layer of FHB-bonded boards is not fully cured and longer press times (20 s/mm) are needed to reach a sufficient degree of curing throughout the cross-section of FHB-particle boards.

The mean density of the test specimen from the particle board produced at 14 s/mm was 619 kg/m^3 and 648 kg/m^3 for the 20 s/mm board (see Fig. 8, B). Spring back ($7.1 \pm 1.3\%$) occurred in the particle boards made with the fructose/HMF/BHMT adhesive at 10 s/mm. This also explains the reduced density and MOR of these samples (Fig. 8).

Fig. 8. Strength development of fructose/HMF/BHMT adhesives (A-C) with a molar ratio of 3.7/0.2/1 60 min (8), 2.5/0.1/1 20 min (7) and 4.9/0.3/1 45 min (?), and fructose/BHMT adhesives (D-F) with a molar ratio of 3.9/1 20 min (v) and 2.6/1 20 min (!) at different press temperatures of 105 °C, 110 °C and 120 °C (always 60 s cooling). A UF adhesive (.) with 15% ammonium nitrate (1:10) was used as the reference.

Fig. 9. Mechanical properties of particle boards bonded by fructose/HMF/BHMT (3.7:0.2:1, 60 min) and commercial UF adhesives. (a) Internal bond strength, (b) density, (c) modulus of elasticity (MOE) and (d) modulus of rupture (MOR). Number of samples = 5.

Fig. 10. (Left): Fructose-HMF-BHMT adhesive (FHB, 3.7/0.2/1, 60 min) used for particle board production, (Middle) darker colored FHB-bonded particle board made at a press factor of 10 s/mm and (Right) FHB-bonded particle board bonded at 20 s/mm. Commercial UF-bonded particle boards are depicted as a reference.

Further, the thickness swelling of the fructose/HMF/BHMT particle boards was significantly higher with $31 \pm 2\%$ at 14 s/mm and $29 \pm 1\%$ at 20 s/mm. The reference boards with UF showed a thickness swelling of $18 \pm 2\%$ at 10 s/mm. The thickness swelling and water absorption for all press factors can be found in the [Supporting Information](#) (Fig. 2). The results clearly demonstrated that the cure speed of fructose/HMF/BHMT adhesive was high enough to ensure a sufficient degree of curing even in the core layer of the board at press factors > 14 s/mm.

Nevertheless, the performance of conventional UF made particle boards was not reached, which is not in alignment with the results of

previous ABES testing. This can have many reasons. The first and foremost is that the production parameters are not optimized for the HMF-containing adhesive whereas standard parameters for production of UF-boards were used (e.g. press temperature 220°C , adhesive amount: 10%). Further, the adhesive was applied to the wood chips by pouring rather than the commonly used spraying method. Also, the UF adhesive has a lower viscosity than fructose/HMF/BHMT, which might cause differences in adhesive distribution within the particle board. In general, the IB is directly influenced by various factors, such as the density of the core layer, the adhesive quantity and distribution as well as the particle

geometry and their properties (Papadopoulos, 2006; Solt; et al., 2019). The observed difference between ABES and particle board testing certainly open up future research avenues, which should explore the effect of other particle board production parameter on the performance.

Fig. 11 depicts the IB values of particle boards produced with fructose/HMF/BHMT adhesive (3.7/0.2/1, 60 min, star symbols) and gives a comparison with other HMF-containing adhesives from literature (Rosenfeld et al., 2020; Solt et al., 2019). The literature IB values should be treated with caution since no standard testing procedure was used or not all the parameters of the manufacturing process were provided in the publications.

The majority of particle boards bonded with carbohydrate-based adhesives need significantly longer press factors (>20 s/mm). The number of particle boards bonded with HMF-containing adhesives is still very low and no differentiation between individual publications was made in Fig. 11. Still, it is important to note that several HMF-bonded particle boards were reported in literature that reached the IB requirement of EN312 after 20–30 s/mm. For example, Avalon Industries reported particle boards made with a urea-HMF adhesive at a press factor of 20–28 s/mm in a patent application. In terms of IB and press factor, the fructose/HMF/BHMT bonded particle boards had a similar performance. A clear advantage of the fructose/HMF/BHMT adhesive is the low amounts of HMF (5%) needed to reach this performance and the realization of the adhesive production in an in-situ process. Thus avoiding the use of pure HMF, which would significantly increase the cost of the adhesive. In comparison, the aforementioned adhesive reported by Avalon Industries has a molar ratio of 1:0.5 (urea:HMF) and is made with pure HMF.

Summarizing, particle boards made with the fructose/HMF/BHMT adhesive (3.7/0.2/1, 60 min) had a good performance even at low press factors (20 s/mm) compared to other carbohydrate-based boards. Still, they did not reach the performance of conventionally used UF-bonded ones. There is still room for further optimization as the influence of manufacturing factors (Halligan, 1970; Kelly, 1977), e.g., adhesive amount and distribution or moisture content. Reducing the needed press factor of FHB-bonded boards to even lower values (10 s/mm) is an important task in the development of a competitive, bio-based adhesive for particle boards. A further optimization of production parameters (adhesive amount, mat moisture content) and press factor will be done in a follow-up publication.

4. Conclusion

In the production of interior-use particle boards the core layer temperature is restricted to below 110 °C during manufacture. For a cleaner production of these boards it is important to develop bio-based adhesives with an enhanced cure speed. In previous publications it was found that HMF reduces the activation energy of the curing reaction of fructose-BHMT adhesives. This work focused on determining whether HMF influences the cure speed and tensile shear strength development of fructose-BHMT adhesives and if there is a composition-property relation that can be used as an adjusting screw to enhance the adhesive efficiency.

Therefore, the temperature-dependent curing behavior was analyzed of adhesives compositions with varying molar ratios. It can be concluded that HMF enhances the development of tensile shear strength in fructose/BHMT adhesive, notably even at moderate temperatures around 105 °C. A linear correlation between tensile shear strength and BHMT amount was found for fructose/BHMT adhesives. This correlation was not observed for fructose/HMF/BHMT adhesives. This suggest that HMF changes the curing reactions for fructose-BHMT adhesives significantly. Overall, there seems to be an optimum molar ratio of fructose/HMF/BHMT with regard to tensile shear strength development.

The best results with regard to cure speed were obtained from adhesives with a molar ratio of fructose/HMF/BHMT = 3.7/0.2/1. In ABES testing the rapid strength development was comparable to conventional

Fig. 11. Internal bond strength perpendicular to the plane for particle boards made of fructose/HMF/BHMT adhesives (ψ) in comparison to other HMF-containing adhesives (Rosenfeld et al., 2020) and carbohydrate-based adhesives (Solt et al., 2019) previously reported in literature. Typical laboratory-made UF particle boards with different formaldehyde-emission classes (E1, F****, AsWood®) (Solt et al., 2019) are included as reference as well.

UF. This is especially notable as the fructose/HMF/BHMT (3.7/0.2/1) adhesive has a high renewable content of 76 mol.-% and requires no formaldehyde addition.

Prototype particle boards were manufactured with the most efficient resin composition in terms of strength development. The high cure speed obtained in ABES testing could not be transported to the IB strength in particle boards. In general, many production parameters, e.g. density, adhesive distribution or mat moisture content can influence the obtained IB values. Therefore, further optimization of the production parameters is necessary for evaluating the potential of fructose/HMF/BHMT adhesive in the particle boards. Overall, quite promising results were obtained even for the non-optimized procedure. The press factor needed to reach the minimum IB of EN319 standard was among the best reported for carbohydrate-based or HMF-based adhesives.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Catherine Rosenfeld: Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis Writing – original draft. **Wilfried Sailer-Kronlachner:** Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **Johannes Konnerth:** Supervision, Resources, Writing – review & editing. **Pia Solt-Rindler:** Writing – review & editing. **Alessandro Pellis:** Resources, Data curation. **Thomas Rosenau:** Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **Antje Potthast:** Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **Hendrikus W.G. van Herwijnen:** Conceptualization, Resources, Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.indcrop.2022.115536](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indcrop.2022.115536).

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